

Zeekflow+: A Deep LSTM Autoencoder with Integrated Random Forest Classifier for Binary and Multi-class Classification in Network Traffic Data

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ABSTRACT

This work proposes Zeekflow+, a Deep LSTM Autoencoder (AE) architecture with integrated Random Forest (RF) classifier for effective binary & multi-class classification of network traffic data. The Deep LSTM AE is used to extract underlying patterns existing within the features of the input data and encode them accordingly, allowing for binary classification to malicious or benign behavior. Through the use of the RF classifier, the binary classification capabilities are extended to multi-class ones for effectively identifying the origin of the attacks. This is achieved by training the RF classifier using the total reconstruction loss and the Deep LSTM AE encoded data. Experimental results on the USTC-TFC2016 dataset, showcase the performance of the Zeekflow+ architecture in multi-class classification resulting in more than 99% in the precision, recall and F1-Score classification metrics. To further demonstrate the effectiveness of the Zeekflow+ architecture, it is used for binary classification task in the same dataset, while considering different Floating Point arithmetic quantizations with the results showing negligible performance drop, making it suitable for real-time IoT edge device deployment.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy → Systems security; • Computing methodologies → Machine learning.

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KEYWORDS

Anomaly Detection, IoT, LSTM AE, Random Forest, Neural Network Quantization, Deep Learning, Network Traffic

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1 INTRODUCTION

Modern Internet of Things (IoT) technologies encompass the integration of diverse sensor elements and actuators targeting seamless intercommunication among them and other computer systems through wired or wireless communication networks [1]. Their inherent connectivity facilitates monitoring of the digital world, and in certain cases, control of the analog one, having strong impact to various sectors of human and economic activities including consumers [13], cities [10], transportation [21], industry [7], medical and healthcare [8], and many others. Yet, with the IoT ecosystem continuously expanding, the needs for robust cybersecurity measures safeguarding against potential threats also increase.

Among several techniques used for enhancing cybersecurity, anomaly detection (AD) is considered a popular one, especially in the case of intrusion detection systems [20]. Specifically, AD algorithms spot outliers, defined as events with significant deviation from a system's normal behavior, which can take the form of singular data points or even whole data-frames within time-series of data [18]. However, the amount of data being generated by the IoT devices and their interconnection, each with varying computing resources, communication protocols, and capacities introduces complexity to the realization of conventional AD algorithms based on statistical analysis. To address such challenges, research has

shifted towards employing Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods and techniques for AD to enhance the operation of the IoT devices in a more sophisticated manner [18, 20].

Within the context of AI methods for AD, traditional approaches take Machine Learning (ML) as a common practice, with k-means clustering, isolation forests and one-class support vector machines (SVM) being the main approaches [2, 11]. However, when the complexity of the inputs increases, these shallow models face difficulties in handling high-dimensional datasets [5]. To further improve the performance, recent advancements explore Deep Learning (DL) approaches, with great emphasis given on Autoencoders (AE) [2]; they are capable to learn compressed representations of input data by forcing them through a bottleneck layer, capturing effectively the underlying patterns and the essential features [22]. Narrowing down to the case of AD in network traffic, utilizing Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models is a suitable approach as the learning procedure can benefit from its inherent ability in handling sequential data, which is exactly the case of network traffic.

The hybrid ML/DL architecture proposed in this work, named Zeekflow+, is a Deep LSTM AE utilizing a Random Forest (RF) classifier for network traffic AD. Through the use of the Deep LSTM AE, underlying patterns originating from the features of the input data can be captured and encoded resulting in effective, binary classification of the nature's data to benign or malicious. With the use of the RF classifier, integrated within the architecture, the binary classification is extended to a multi-class one, thus expanding its capabilities.

2 RELATED WORK

Building on top of the AE foundation, in [12] authors propose the inclusion of specific regularizer within the AE models so as to concentrate normal data points in a central region of interest corresponding to the learned representations, pushing anomalies further away [17]. This method offers advantages in performance, robustness, and efficiency for anomaly detection, particularly with sparse network traffic data. Another approach, [16], detects distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks by leveraging both time-based features and AEs, achieved using various time windows within the AE architecture. As such, improved identification of different DDoS attack types is achieved. The approach in [4] is a two-step unsupervised approach for anomaly detection. Firstly, authors leverage a Deep Sparse AE to extract key features from network traffic to capture the normal patterns. Secondly, they calculate deviations from these patterns, measured through reconstruction errors, to identify potential anomalies. Using this method allows for anomaly detection without the needs for pre-labeled data.

Beyond individual AE techniques being limited to DL only, recent approaches have explored the combination of both DL and ML, leading to the development of hybrid methods [3, 6, 9, 14, 15]. These methods leverage the strengths of different techniques to achieve improved performance; they use AEs in the DL part for learning informative, compressed representations of the input features [2] and different algorithms in the ML part for classification tasks [11]. An approach using this hybrid method is cited in [6], where an anomaly detection framework combining AE and random forests for an IoT network is proposed, showing enhanced anomaly detection

performance. In the same context, in [9], authors propose the use of sequential, "stacked", AEs for anomaly detection in web application traffic, resulting in allowing the model to learn increasingly complex representations of the data. Once learned, the architecture uses different ML algorithms for classification including Isolation Forests and One-Class Support Vector Machines (SVMs), enhancing the web attacks detection. One specific type of AE gaining attraction is the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based AE [14, 15]. It leverages the LSTM's ability in handling sequential data, like network traffic, by capturing long-term dependencies within them [15]. Following this approach, in [14], authors propose an LSTM AE that incorporates One-Class SVM. LSTM models were trained exclusively on instances of normal classes to recognize typical traffic pattern and the input data's compressed representation, or latent features, while the One-Class SVM was used for binary classification. The experimental findings demonstrate that the suggested model offers a greater detection rate and greatly shortens processing times.

In the proposed work we follow the hybrid ML/DL approach, proposing Zeekflow+. Initially we use the Deep LSTM AE to capture and encode important input features. Then we feed the label encoded representation along with the total reconstruction loss and then feed these representations to the RF classifier, along with the total reconstruction loss corresponding to the aggregated loss of the DNN AE and the LSTM AE, to train the RF classifier. In this way, we achieve: 1) improved performance compared to using only the encoded representation or relying solely on the total reconstruction loss; and 2) expand the binary classification capabilities of the Deep LSTM AE to a multi-class one using the RF classifier.

3 PROPOSED ZEEKFLOW+ ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture for malicious network flow monitoring, named Zeekflow+, is shown in Fig. 1. Its inputs are information in the form of logs extracted from NetFlow and Zeek tools, both originating from the network traffic data. The former, NetFlow, is used to capture structural aspects of the network traffic data by utilizing statistical features, whereas the latter, Zeek, is used to extract history matrices for each communication session between devices, thus collecting information about its past states and events over time. The output of Zeekflow+ serves as an anomaly estimator, capable of identifying and indicating whether a network flow is malicious along with the classification of the attack or benign.

From an information processing perspective, Zeekflow+ utilizes two distinct Deep Learning (DL) models, namely Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and Deep Neural Network (DNN) Autoencoders (AE) as well as a Machine Learning (ML) one, a Random Forest classifier. In the encoding path, the Zeek logs are fed to the LSTM AE so as to capture the dynamic behavior of the communication session history matrices and consequently to find patterns that change over time, reflecting on the states that each network connection travels through. Note that the encoding path consists of layers, each formed of a number of LSTM cells equivalent to the total number of potential connection states. As a result, the LSTM AE accomplishes dimensionality reduction as the data moves through each layer, thus reducing the amount of information in the input while maintaining pertinent temporal information. The last cell of the last layer, i.e. the LSTM AE's output, provides a full representation of the state and

Figure 1: Zeekflow+ Architecture.

temporal dynamics of the network connection by encapsulating all the important information learnt from the sequential data.

Once the information from Zeek log are encoded, they are concatenated with the NetFlow logs, ready to be processed by the DNN AE. Its purpose is to enhance the capabilities of the LSTM AE by processing additional input modalities, like metadata or static information, all associated with the network traffic instances. The DNN AE captures high-level characteristics useful to anomaly detection and learns non-linear modifications of the input data, thereby creating an accurate latent representation by combining the statistical information from the NetFlow tool with the temporal representation from the LSTM AE’s encoding path. Even though these features are combined, they play distinct roles in the reconstruction process and are not dependent on each other. Interestingly, the quality of the model’s reconstruction of the original input data is measured by reconstructing both the NetFlow features and the Zeek history matrix. Through this procedure, the model learns to reconstruct benign data closely resembling its training samples. On the other hand, the reconstruction greatly differs from the input when malicious or anomalous data is introduced into the model, indicating the existence of an anomaly behavior. It should be noted that ZeekFlow+’s architecture ensures symmetry in the reconstruction process by mirroring the encoding path’s structure, meaning that the decoding part of the LSTM AE is identical to that of the encoding part.

The above process described provides with a binary classification of the inputs’ nature, that is malicious or benign. Specifically, by considering two reconstruction losses, one for the LSTM AE and one for the DNN AE, estimation of an existing anomaly is received. Yet, in the case of a malicious attack, its type is unknown. To this end, Zeekflow+ incorporates a Random Forest (RF) classifier in the heart of its processing core with the purpose of expanding its

anomaly detection capabilities. It applies semi-supervised training methodology to its AE-based feature learning so as to enable multi-class classification in the case of malicious attacks. During training phase, every labeled encoded representation functions as a feature vector and along with the total reconstruction loss from the DNN and the LSTM AE, forms the basis for training the RF classifier. In return the RF classifier divides instances of encoded network traffic into discrete groups, distinguishing between legitimate activity and different kinds of network attacks. An illustration of the anomaly detection’s procedure is shown in Fig. 2

Figure 2: Zeekflow+ Anomaly Detection procedure.

4 EVALUATION OF THE ZEEKFLOW+ ARCHITECTURE

4.1 Experimental Setup

The performance evaluation of the proposed Zeekflow+ architecture is done using the USTC-TFC2016 dataset [19], a popular botnet attack dataset suitable for anomaly detection purposes. It consists

Table 1: USTC-TFC2016 Dataset

Benign Traffic		Malicious Traffic	
Dataset	Records	Dataset	Records
Facetime	6,000	Tinba	21,000
Skype	12,000	Zeus	86,000
BitTorrent	15,000	Shifu	500,000
Gmail	25,000	Neris	499,218
Outlook	15,000	Cridex	461,548
WoW	140,000	Nsis-ay	351,000
MySQL	200,000	Geodo	213,000
FTP	360,000	Miuref	81,000
SMB	925,453	Virut	437,000
Weibo	1,210,000	Htbot	169,000
Total	2,908,513	Total	2,818,766

of two parts; one containing malware traffic from public websites and one containing normal traffic from different information exchange tools. Both parts along with their number of records are shown in detail in Table 1. Considering the training/test split case, the benign part of the dataset was used for training and testing purposes, corresponding to 80% and 20% of the dataset respectively. By doing so, we effectively ensure i) that the proposed Zeekflow+ architecture can capture the characteristics of normal network behavior thus establishing a baseline for identifying anomalies and ii) that the 20% of the benign traffic can serve as a negative control for assessing the model’s ability in correctly identifying normal network behavior. Moreover, the entire part of the malicious dataset was used to evaluate the model’s capacity to detect anomalous activities associated with potential attacks.

With the proposed architecture having two distinct losses, it is reasonable to provide further detail on this. Specifically, to evaluate the accuracy of the NetFlow characteristics reconstruction, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) is used as it targets a regression task with the goal of reducing the gap between the predicted, \mathbf{x}' , and actual values, \mathbf{x} . On the contrary, the reconstruction of each matrix history state of Zeek requires to classify each state based on its one-hot encoding representation, therefore, the reconstruction process is assessed using the Categorical Cross-Entropy (CCE) loss. Both losses are aggregated by weighted addition to provide the total reconstruction loss as

$$L_T = w_{MSE}L_{MSE} + w_{CCE}L_{CCE}. \tag{1}$$

Once calculated, the total reconstruction loss from (1) is used along with the encodings from the DNN AE as inputs to the RF classifier to drive its training procedure. This is achieved by labeling according to the original category (benign or type of malicious activity) from the testing dataset. As such, necessary ground truth information for training and evaluation of the RF classifier is provided. It should be noted that training and testing of the Deep LSTM AE and the RF classifier is done sequentially, namely first the Deep LSTM AE and then the RF classifier, in order to enrich the input information of the latter.

Considering the structure of the networks, each one is described as follows: the LSTM AE comprises three encoding layers with hidden layer sizes of 100, 50, and 10, and an input size of 177, whereas the encoding layers follow a converse size, i.e., 10, 50, 100. With respect to the DNN AE, the encoding path comprises of 128/64/32 linear layers, all activated with leaky ReLU with negative slope having value $\alpha = 0.3$, while the decoding path follows conversely, that is with 32/64/128 linear layer size. Note that batch normalization is applied between the linear layers of the encoding path only. As far as the rest parameters are concerned, the batch size used was 32, the learning rate was 0.01 and the number of training iterations was 101. The proposed architecture has in total 240, 554 trainable parameters. On the RF classifier part, it consists of 100 estimators (trees), while the rest of its parameters are set to default.

To measure the performance of the proposed Zeekflow+ architecture, the following classification metrics we used:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \tag{3}$$

$$\text{F1-Score} = \frac{2\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}, \tag{4}$$

where TP, FP, FN correspond to True Positive (TP), False Positive (FP) and False Negative (FN) respectively. Note that within the context of network traffic assessment, the Recall evaluation metric corresponds to the true alarm rate (or sensitivity) of a model.

4.2 Experimental Results

We showcase the performance of the Zeekflow+ architecture in multi-class classification by considering the following three cases for the RF classifier’s training; a) we feed only the encodings to the RF classifier; b) we feed only the total reconstruction loss to the RF classifier c) we feed both the encodings and the total reconstruction loss to the RF classifier. The results using (2), (3) and (4) are shown in Table 2. It can be observed that in case c), Zeekflow+ yields the highest classification metric results in most of the 10 available classes, followed by case a) which are only a few. Apparently, using only the total reconstruction loss, case b), results in the lowest performance among the three cases. With the above, it can be concluded that feeding both the encodings and the total reconstruction loss improves further the classification capabilities of the RF classifier.

We further explore the performance of the proposed Zeekflow+ architecture in binary classification tasks, under the scope of edge IoT deployment. To that end, we consider different Floating Point (FP) arithmetic quantization for both the weights and the architecture’s inputs during Zeekflow+’s testing. The FP64 arithmetic is the baseline number representation, while FP32 and FP16 are the targeted quantization levels under exploration. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3. It can be seen that despite quantizing the model’s weights and the inputs from FP64 to FP32 and FP16 arithmetic, the classification metrics have negligible drop in performance, also supported by the Area Under Curve (AUC) score being approx. 0.91 in all cases. Moreover, the quantization also impacts the architecture’s size as when the model size is reduced, its size in MB is also

Table 2: Classification results for three different RF classifier training cases of the Zeekflow+ architecture in the USTC-TFC2016 dataset

Class	Encodings			Total Reconstruction Loss			Encodings and Total Reconstruction Loss		
	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1	Precision	Recall	F1
Normal	99.51	99.89	99.7	94.9	94.53	94.72	99.77	99.9	99.83
Cridex	99.6	99.80	99.70	79.5	80.89	80.19	99.66	99.80	99.73
Geodo	99.71	99.94	99.83	55.18	54.83	55.0	99.77	99.95	99.86
Miuref	99.05	99.09	99.07	37.95	39.32	38.62	99.23	99.35	99.29
Htbot	99.22	98.97	99.10	37.03	37.32	37.17	99.14	99.57	99.36
Neris	99.89	99.06	99.47	21.34	20.7	21.02	99.81	99.10	99.46
Nsis-ay	99.36	97.58	98.46	21.58	21.97	21.77	99.61	98.91	99.25
Shifu	99.73	99.93	99.83	16.35	17.01	16.67	99.66	99.93	99.80
Tinba	99.73	99.64	99.68	47.75	47.25	47.5	99.73	99.77	99.75
Virut	99.72	99.5	99.61	56.34	56.35	56.35	99.75	99.51	99.63
Zeus	99.01	98.89	98.95	43.39	42.48	42.93	99.32	99.18	99.25

Figure 3: Binary classification results using different Floating Point quantization for the Zeekflow+ architecture

reduced; compared to the baseline FP64 being 1.9 MB, when the model reduces to FP32 its size drops to 0.92 MB, corresponding to 51.57% reduction from the baseline and when it reduces to FP16 its size drops to 0.45 MB corresponding to 76.31% reduction from the baseline .

5 CONCLUSIONS

A Deep LSTM AE architecture with integrated RF classifier for both binary & multi-class classification, named Zeekflow+, was proposed in this work. Experimental results on the USTC-TFC2016 dataset demonstrated its effectiveness multi-class classification, resulting

in more than 99% in precision, recall, F1-score metrics. Further more, in the binary classification case, quantizing model weight and inputs to FP16 representation demonstrated negligible drop in performance, making the model suitable for compact IoT edge deployment. For our future work we will consider to benchmark Zeekflow+ with similar architectures under the same dataset to ensure fair results.

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